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Development and Acceptability of Breadnut Seed (*Artocarpus camansi*) Polvoron

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Abstract.

This study focused on the development and evaluation of Breadnut Seed (*Artocarpus camansi*) Polvoron as a functional food product with enhanced nutritional value and consumer acceptability. The study aimed to formulate three (3) variations of breadnut seed polvoron and to assess their sensory characteristics, acceptability, significant differences among formulations, and nutritional composition.

A developmental research design employing exploratory and descriptive approaches was utilized. The product development phase involved formulating polvoron with varying proportions of breadnut seed flour (100%, 50%, and 25%), followed by food critique, sensory evaluation by expert panelists, and nutritional analysis. Consumer acceptability testing was conducted among 120 respondents, comprising food experts, students, and general consumers, using a 9-point hedonic scale to evaluate color/appearance, aroma, flavor/taste, sweetness, texture, and overall acceptability. Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to analyze the data.

Findings revealed that most respondents were young, single, female, and college-level individuals. All three formulations were generally described as light brown, with a distinct nutty aroma and flavor, and moderate sweetness. In terms of acceptability, all formulations were rated from "Like Moderately" to "Like Very Much," with Formulation C consistently obtaining the highest sensory ratings. Significant differences were observed among the formulations in most sensory attributes, except aroma. Formulation C emerged as the most

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preferred formulation based on overall composite appeal. However, acceptability did not vary significantly across age groups and was generally consistent across sexes, except for texture and composite appeal. Nutritional analysis showed that Formulation C is a low-calorie, carbohydrate-dominant snack with minimal fat and negligible protein content.

The study concludes that breadnut seed can be successfully utilized in polvoron production, with Formulation C identified as the most acceptable variant. The developed product demonstrates potential for functional food innovation and commercialization, while further improvement in nutritional content and texture is recommended.

Keywords: *Breadnut seed, polvoron, sensory evaluation, acceptability, functional food, product development*